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**Why Change Works so Slowly?
Occupational Choices of Women in STEM Between Motivational Strategies and
Societal Gender Backlash**

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ABSTRACT

The amount of first year students in Germany in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) fields is rapidly increasing. In winter term 2015, 40% of all first-year students chose a STEM study programme, from whereas 70% were male and 30% female. Ongoing initiatives and motivation projects by industry and science running now for years seem to have measurable impacts, though not in favoured speed and not in favoured amount.

This paper ought to bring some light on the relationship between the development of women's proportions in STEM and the occupational choices of women as well as looking at opposing trends: While the motivational activities seem to become successful, girls and young women are made insecure again in terms of their gender and professional roles by a gender backlash. This gender backlash is visible for instance in gendered toys, a refusal of research results of Gender Studies (in STEM and in general), a public debate about "the freedom of choice" for girls back into gender stereotyped job options, combined with well-known argumentations about their lack of mathematical skills and interest observable in Germany and all over Europe.

Conference Key Areas: Gender and Diversity; Attractiveness of Engineering Education; Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Motivation projects, university-industry co-operation, women in STEM programmes, gender backlash

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INTRODUCTION

In 2015, Germany had more first year students than ever before. 40% of them chose a STEM study programme [2], from whereas 70% were male and 30% female [2]. This means we exceeded the limit of marginalization [3], where a minority group does not express to feel as minority any longer and the single woman is not addressed as representative for all women (in STEM) anymore. The initiatives and motivation projects run over years by industry and science seem to show first effects, though not in favoured speed and not in favoured amount. Was this amount of new female STEM students a singular peak in the statistics or is it the beginning of a repeatable success?

A study on behalf of the “Arbeitgeberverband Gesamtmetall” (Federation of German Employers' Associations in the Metal and Electrical Engineering Industries) [1] shows the relationship between the development in STEM to open for more girls and women and the occupational choices of women. It documents the potency of systematic and evaluated run of several motivational projects based on scientific results about Gender and STEM. In consistency, recommended action was formulated to make the best practice projects more visible and transferable.

At the same time in Germany and all over Europe we observe the phenomenon of a gender backlash. This is shown e.g. by gendered toys [4], a refusal of research results of Gender Studies (in STEM and in general), a public debate about “the freedom of choice” for girls into gender stereotyped job options, combined with well-known argumentations about their lack of mathematical skills and interests. That means: At the same time where motivational activities seem to become successful, girls and young women are made insecure again in terms of their gender and professional roles.

With respect to the conference topic, this research paper therefore longs to show results about all three sides: The successful motivational activities and rising numbers of female first year students and how study programme choices are made today as well as examples of backlash activities in Germany and Europe.

1 EFFECTIVENESS OF INITIATIVES FOR MORE WOMEN IN STEM

1.1 Goals of the study

In Industry, Science and Society we find three guiding themes in debates and initiatives for more women in STEM:

- A lack of personnel in technical fields, especially in Informatics / Digitalization, Mechanical and Electrical Engineering;
- Innovation strategies, finding scientific and economic potential between disciplines (interdisciplinary) and in stronger diversity of personnel in Research and Development;
- Equal opportunity as a political strategy to offer women and men, and as well people from diverse social classes, ages, with diverse cultural or educational background, same access to education and professions.

These three guiding themes influence each other and are the starting point for initiatives to motivate women to choose a STEM profession and to stay successful in in-plant training, studies and profession.

Our study had the mission to work out the state of the scientific knowledge, to describe the actual project situation and to find out gaps and recommended actions to optimize the activities.

In a first step, desk research was conducted whereas consisting of the acquisition and analysis of existing data material and research results. The disadvantage of desk research, which is only existing research can be analysed [5], proved to be an advantage for this project, as the existing gaps in research become visible. In the desk research process, over 260 contemporary sources were categorized along the influence factors as well as the learning places school, enterprise / training enterprises and university. To this end, the present studies are analysed, the desired and undesired

interactions between these three levels were elaborated and gaps in research identified.

As next step, the current project practice in the field of scholars, professional orientation and STEM was highlighted. Hence a research in the project databases of central actors in the STEM area (“National Pact for Women in STEM” and “Navigator of STEM initiatives” at “MINT Zukunft schaffen” (“make STEM future”)) as well as an experts workshop and two subsequent reflection discussions on the project selection and project typology structures were conducted. Together with detailed research and surveys of the STEM projects and offers in the field girls - vocational orientation - STEM and a standardised survey of all about 1080 projects, a total of 51 STEM projects were analysed and processed into detailed profiles. This enabled us to identify best practice typologies and representative projects, programmes and measures for educational purposes.

In the following sub-sections we present our scientific results on learning institutions schools, universities and finally by societal factors influencing occupational choices. Results regarding enterprises and their in-plant trainings are left out with respect to the conference topics.

1.2 Findings about school impact on occupational choices for STEM

Boys and girls show the same performance in STEM [6]. But over the phases of childhood a gender difference on STEM interest is proved [7][8]. At school, teachers take over a relevant role as agents for socialisation. Teachers have a central function in “doing gender” processes [9] and are relevant gatekeepers in the development of STEM interest and motivation [10]. Female teachers in STEM (e.g. physics) are acting as role models [11][12]. Positive relationships between female scholars and teachers strengthen this role model function [12]. If teachers act in a way gender blind and insensitive, girls may develop gendered preferences. Gender stereotypes about abilities, competencies and preferences work on their self-performance expectation and influence the choice of favourite subjects [10].

If female students at school choose STEM subjects this develops a positive effect on their self-performance expectation and motivation [14]. But in this decision phase, the scholars are also in their adolescent phase and very focussed on gender related behaviour. Therefore, gender stereotypes for vocational decisions become more relevant [15] and lead them to a gender specific self-selection [16]. First scientific results about the effectiveness of motivation measures in this field are available (e.g. [17][14], handouts for implementation and evaluation of STEM measures [18]), but these results are unfortunately not comprehensively used in programmes, projects and measures yet.

The next step on the way towards a gender sensitive professional orientation on a strategical level is to implement the knowledge about gender and STEM into the curricula for teachers and to develop gender balanced teaching material. Schools need to formulate their gender sensitive goals for professional orientation into their statutes in order to plan, act and check their measures. Here a wide spread of societies and initiatives exists to combine school curricular activities with extra-curricular projects (see for example the internet platform of the National Pact for Women in STEM [19]).

1.3 Findings about university impact on occupational choices for STEM

The number of qualified and interested young women in STEM increased over the last years constantly. But even though they have better school diploma than men in average, this does not correlate yet in their applications for STEM study programmes [20]: In the winter term 2016/17 we had 48% women in the first semester over all, but in STEM 32% [21]. This relatively positive development in STEM and especially in Engineering shows that the activities and programmes of universities and departments over the last years are successful. Untypical study programmes become more attractive for women [16], also for those who didn't mention a STEM field as interesting earlier. It demonstrates as well that the female self-effacement bases on structural and cultural reasons and not on individual preferences [22].

Children from non-academic families, from families with low income and with migration background have still smaller chances to achieve a university degree [23]. Women with STEM affinity out of these fields demonstrate high motivation to start into a STEM study programme because they hope for social advancement. This group would therefore be a promising target group for recruiting STEM talents if systematically considered [23].

Universities and STEM departments offer a wide range of projects and measures to motivate women for STEM. Only some of them set changes in own working cultures, programme settings, content or didactical elements [24]. In many cases the projects, like summer schools or women-only courses, take place outside the universities mainstream programme. Linking to digitalization the mentoring programme “Cybermentor” matches around 800 female scholars per year with female students and research assistants online. The evaluation shows that 71% of the participants decide for STEM study programmes afterwards.

In some federal states of Germany, long-term interventions between industry and universities for female school graduates started (e.g. Lower Sachsony “Technikum”, Hesse “Technikum”, North Rhine-Westphalia “zdi-Campus”). They offer a combination of half year-trial study and industrial placement. This also seems to be successful: From 94 placement participants (“Technikantinnen”) in Lower Sachsony 2016, 89% decided for engineering professions.

Next step in this field would be a role out of women-only courses for all STEM departments and universities. Also, the state initiatives seem to be on a good way to convince interested women who are still unsure if STEM professions would be a professional perspective for them. Long-term online offers have a high range especially for women from rural areas. Scaled and structured information in combination with practical experience offers young women good chances for STEM decisions, particularly when they come from non-academic and low-income families. There lies still potential for more diverse research.

1.4 Findings about societal impact and backlash effects on occupational choices for STEM

The occupational choice process depends on several direct and indirect influences and interdependencies, described as a „multi-factorial process“ [25][26].

Gender stereotypes and different socialisation of boys and girls influence the occupational choice processes directly. In comparison to boys, girls have low experience with mathematics, natural science and engineering. Therefore, they develop later less knowledge and interest in STEM fields [16]. Their technical self-performance expectation and their self-assessment belonging their STEM performance is therefore often lower as it is shown from boys [14].

Gatekeepers, like teachers, vocational advisers and role models, have shown to have a great influence in the technical socialisation of girls and young women, as mentioned before. Parents and family members have a key function because they are not only the consultants for their children in vocational choice processes but also they impress the interests and abilities of their daughters with estimation, household work division, own affinity for science and engineering and through transferring their own perception of gender roles to their children [28].

STEM professions have a more and more relevant and active part forming economical and societal developments [29]. But young women (and men) do only have small knowledge about tangible working fields. Therefore, they are not able to estimate the societal relevance of these professions [8]. From their perspective, STEM professions are far from society and humans. Their image is still male connoted [30]. This perspective is intensified by media and by job titles, focussing the technical parts of occupation [8][10][28].

This is the context of “Industry 4.0”, on the one hand discussed as a chance for new and flexible work places and on the other as a risk in matters of “atypical” working requirements like mobility, entrepreneurship or digitalization as danger for human skills and work places. This all together affects occupational choice processes indirectly

[28][31].

Several nation-wide initiatives and campaigns try to raise the percentage of women in STEM. 1.7 million girls participated at the “Girls’ Day” since 2001, each year schools and enterprises offer more than 10’000 STEM-oriented activities. Teaching material for schools was developed and used for preparation before and after the events. Evaluations show that a lot of the participants continue to come back every year. The “National pact for women in STEM professions”, founded by industry, science, media, professional associations and the Federal Ministry for Education and Science (BMBF) in 2008 today builds a network of more than 230 partners to support a lot of nation-wide projects and activities at the several levels of the occupational choice process, as outlined in the chapters before.

While schools, industry, university and politics figure out best intervention for the STEM decision making for girls and young women and be more and more successful, a public debate started concerning gender roles and a “freedom of choice“ for girls in gender typical professions. This debate is dominated by conservative and right-wing parties and their focal point on “re-traditionalism” of society. In their opinion, gender and diversity research practices manipulative brainwashing especially for men and women in case of their “natural” roles, abilities and interests [32]. In respectable newspapers, we read about girls who would be incompetent and incurious in math but treated into STEM; boys on the other hand would be better in school if they could act as “real men” and taught by male teachers. Journalists in TV talk shows explain that their own children always used gendered toys “naturally”. Politicians stand up saying that all projects and initiatives of the last years wouldn’t come to more women in STEM but instead only waste a lot of money. They all share a picture of “good old times” with traditionalistic gender roles, which does not stand on a historical basis but serves societal emotions.

That means: At the same time where motivational activities seem to become successful, girls and young women are made insecure again in terms of their gender and professional roles.

2 GENDER MINT 4.0: A LONGITUDE STUDY ON STUDENT TRANSITION FROM SCHOOL TO UNIVERSITY

Hence, we conduct an ongoing longitude study, founded by BMBF and supported by the social partners, professional associations, universities and other actors in this field, on the transition of women into STEM degree programmes from high school to university. The ongoing study examines the effects of different influences on the study choice and the study success of women in STEM, how gender and diversity-oriented change processes in universities and enterprises work in this context and how the interactions of the various influences on the process of career choices. To this end, a method mix of quantitative and qualitative social research is implemented: Students at High School, STEM Students at university, companies and universities are surveyed and interviewed to examine the course of studies and the career advancement of women and men in STEM fields in a deepening and comprehensive manner and to identify relevant cultural and structural changes in universities and enterprises. The results will lead to recommendations for the improvement of measures for gender and diversity-related generation of young people and serve the development of a specific further training format for actors in STEM fields. First results are expected to be available at the SEFI Annual Conference in September 2017.

3 CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that the next strategic step towards a gender sensitive professional orientation requires the implementation of profound knowledge about gender and STEM in curricula and teaching materials. These ought to be developed further. Furthermore for universities and departments in STEM it would be recommended to offer more women.only courses. Also there is still a desideratum at STEM decisions and the link to structured information and practical experiences, especially concerning students from non-academic and low-income families. We are looking forward to the

first results from the project "GenderMINT 4.0".

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